

D9.3 Urban Circular Biobased Quality Label communication pack

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Description
CCRI	EU Circular Cities & Regions Initiative
HOOP	Hub of circular cities bOOsting Platform to foster investments for the valorisation of urban biowaste and wastewater
OFMSW	Organic Fraction of Municipal Solid Waste
UCBH	Urban Circular Bioeconomy Hub
UWWS	Urban Wastewater Sludge
VA	Virtual Academy

Executive summary

The HOOP project supports eight Lighthouse Cities and Regions to develop large-scale urban circular bioeconomy initiatives that will focus on making bio-based products from the organic fraction of municipal solid waste (OFMSW) and urban wastewater sludge (UWWS).

Within the action, partners are developing a circular ranking system for cities and regions. This assessment system enables cities and regions to find out how 'circular' their territory is. Nine possible 'levels' can be obtained depending on performance. These levels (CL1 to CL9; reflective of the TRL ranking) can be interpreted as a set of recommended steps to reach a real and effective Urban Circular Bioeconomy and will serve cities as an instrument to understand their current position/performance in regard to the implementation of circular measures at city level.

The circularity level will be made visible by means of an actual label (digital and physical) in order to promote and disseminate the environmental awareness of the cities. The design of this label is the responsibility of Greenovate! Europe within Task 9.2 of the Action and is the subject of this document.

The aim of this document is to share the first designs for the HOOP Circularity Label as well as some instructions for how the label should be used in different digital and physical formats. A design for a basic 'Membership Label' is presented, which would be available for all members of the HOOP Network of Cities and Regions. The 'Circularity Label' would be a variation of this Membership Label, with different coloured options representing the different circularity levels.

It should be noted however that, according to the work schedule presented in the Grant Agreement, the methodology linked to the Circularity Levels is still in an early development stage and only expected to be ready by September 2022. Therefore, it must be understood that this document presents draft examples of the Label, while a definitive version will be presented in a future update of Deliverable 9.3.

1. Introduction

1.1. The HOOP project

The HOOP Project will help to unlock bio-based investments and deploy local bio economies in Europe through a systemic and cross-cutting approach. It offers Project Development Assistance to a group of 8 Lighthouse Cities and Regions to build the technical, economic, financial and legal expertise needed to develop concrete investments to valorise Organic Fraction of Municipal Solid Waste (OFMSW) or Urban Wastewater Sludge (UWWS) with the aim of obtaining safe and sustainable bio-based products.

For this purpose, HOOP will provide Project Development Assistance (PDA) to Albano-Laziale (Italy), Almere (The Netherlands), Bergen Region (Norway), Kuopio (Finland), Münster (Germany), Murcia (Spain), Greater Porto Region (Portugal), and Western Macedonia (Greece).

The Lighthouses were selected among European cities and regions to provide the major possible variety of demographic, climatic and socio-economic conditions, and their role is to be a model for other cities and regions across Europe to replicate the solutions adopted.

Another strategic objective of the HOOP project is to give visibility to the actions taken in the Lighthouses and to foster urban circular bioeconomy more widely across Europe. To this purpose, the HOOP project has created the HOOP Network of Cities and Regions (<https://hoopproject.eu/network/>). This is an open network with already around 30 members. By the end of the project more than 100 cities and regions are expected to participate.

By joining the network, cities and regions gain access to information about innovative urban bioeconomy solutions through services such as the HOOP Virtual Academy, which will compile practical resources across relevant topics. Cities and regions will also engage in knowledge sharing activities relevant to their context and specific interests. Participants have direct exchanges with the 8 HOOP Lighthouse Cities and Regions, sharing experiences and expertise.

1.2. The HOOP Circularity Label

Within Task 7.1 of the Action, partners BaxCo, CETENMA, SAV and ITENE are developing a circular ranking system for cities and regions. This assessment system enables cities and regions to find out how 'circular' their territory is. Nine possible 'levels' can be obtained depending on performance. These levels (CL1 to CL9; reflective of the TRL ranking) can be interpreted as a set of recommended steps to reach a real and effective Urban Circular Bioeconomy and will serve cities as an instrument to understand their current position/performance in regard to the implementation of circular measures at local level. Moreover, it will serve as the baseline to efficiently launch green policies at city level and to effectively boost and implement investment projects for the production of urban biowaste and wastewater-based products.

Work is ongoing to develop the indicators for these circularity levels, which will be tested and validated on the eight HOOP Lighthouse Cities and Regions. The final methodology will be presented in D7.1 'Set of criteria and thresholds for the Urban Circular Biobased Quality Label' which is due by M24 (September 2022). This deliverable will also explain exactly how cities and regions can apply for the label, which is expected to be through the completion of an online form.

The circularity level will be made visible by means of an actual label (digital and physical) in order to promote and disseminate the environmental awareness of the cities. The design of this label is the responsibility of Greenovate! Europe within Task 9.2 of the Action and is the subject of this document.

1.3. Aim of this document

The aim of this document is to share the first designs for the HOOP Circularity Label as well as some instructions for how the label should be used in different digital and physical formats.

It should be noted however that, according to the work schedule presented in the Grant Agreement, the Circularity Levels and Task 7.1 is still in an early development stage and only expected to be ready by September 2022. **Therefore, it must be understood that this document presents draft examples of the Label, while a definitive version will be presented in a future update of Deliverable 9.3.**

2. The Membership Label

2.1. The layout

Any city, region, waste management or water management company can join the HOOP Network of Cities and Regions (<https://hooproject.eu/network/>). Their expression of interest must be validated through an application process led by ACR+ to confirm their membership.

To increase the use of the Circularity Label and promotion of HOOP, it is proposed that **all cities and regions that are members of the HOOP Network are eligible to use a basic version of the Circularity Label**, actually a Membership label.

The following image is a **draft example** of a potential basic Label to be used by all network members:

Figure 1. Draft example of the basic Membership Label. Source: REVOLVE

This basic version of the Label would be the same for all Members, there is no hierarchy and it is intended as a membership badge.

2.2. Use examples for the label

From the HOOP label draft above (see Figure 1), numerous communication derivatives are proposed for different usages, for example as magnet pins for jacket or shirt labels (shown below), for coasters for mugs or glass to rest upon a table, for e-signatures and social media cards, for posters/flyers, and other examples yet to be determined.

Figure 2. Communication derivatives of the Membership Label. Source: REVOLVE

These examples will be developed further with HOOP Partners in order to expand the Network more effectively and to have greater continuity with the flow of the different levels of the Urban Circularity Label process.

3. The Circularity Label

Members of the HOOP Network of Cities and Regions will be encouraged to discover their ‘circularity level’ as explained in Section 1.2.

After they have completed the process and ascertained their circularity level they will be able to ‘upgrade’ their label to reflect their level. As explained already, these levels and associated indicators are still under development, therefore it is not possible to present final designs for the labels at this stage.

For example, the following issues are still under discussion:

- *How the circularity level should be reflected in the label: Task 7.1 of the Action states that “Cities with a CL7 to CL9 will be awarded with the HOOP Circularity Label (bronze, silver and gold, respectively)”. However, subsequent discussions have found this arrangement sub-optimal for a number of reasons. Firstly, only rewarding cities and regions who rank very highly (CL7 to CL9) may be disheartening for cities and regions who are only starting their circular journey and are not able to attain those levels in the short term. Secondly, bronze, silver and gold are very classical signifiers of achievement and are not very suitable for an innovative, inclusive project such as HOOP.*
- *How to reflect differences in biowaste and wastewater management: It is often the case that a city/region performs very well in managing one of the aforementioned waste streams, and quite badly in the other one. As a result, a non-differentiating badge would reflect an average Circularity level, which could be misleading. Since the scope of the Network is to highlight excellence as a source of inspiration, the need of two circularity labels (one for water management, one for biowaste) arose.*

Being Task 7.1 a work in progress, the Circularity levels cannot be defined yet and all the related visuals to add to the basic version of the label neither. Actually, the Circularity levels need to be aligned to the basic label for proper branding.

A first design has been made using a variation on the ‘bronze, silver, gold’ approach (see Figure 3). Within this potential system CL1-3 = blue badge, CL4-6 = green badge, and CL7-9: yellow badge. This arrangement means that all cities and regions receive some kind of recognition, even if their circularity level is relatively low.

These are purely included as examples and final versions will be presented in an updated version of this deliverable.

Figure 3. Examples of potential labels including circularity levels. Source: REVOLVE

Building on these early drafts, it will be important to explore the full journey of achieving and participating in the Circularity Levels so that HOOP Network members can be incentivised to not only be part of the Network but also engage in showing what level they are at and what level they may strive to reach.

4. How to use the label: communication guidelines

As an initial step to the Onboarding process for existing and new members to the HOOP Network of Cities and Regions, each member will receive a Communication Kit that will provide the basic guidelines for how to deploy the label on their channels and platforms as well as the different communication assets to use. Some examples to appear in the Guidelines include:

Communication Guidelines Notes

“Welcome to the HOOP Network of Cities and Regions! We are delighted that you have joined us on this journey to vitalise Europe’s urban bioeconomy.”

As you move towards communicating about your involvement in the HOOP Network, please find below some pointers for using the materials attached to these guidelines:

1. HOOP spelling: when communicating about being a HOOP Network Member, always use capitals for HOOP and for Network, for example:

We are proud to be part of the HOOP Network or **We are a proud member of the HOOP Network** or **[your city or region name] is a member of the HOOP Network**.

2. Email signature: feel free to add the rectangle .jpg or .png banner for e-signatures attached to the bottom of your e-signature with link to <https://hooproject.eu/network/>
3. HOOP banner: use the .jpg or .png HOOP banner attached on your website under your /about section for example and/or in your newsletter (if applicable), always with link to: <https://hooproject.eu/network/>
4. HOOP membership label: you can use the basic version of the HOOP label for your social media profile images for example or you can add the label to a website post with link to: <https://hooproject.eu/network/>.
5. HOOP Circularity label: we encourage you to to assess your Circularity Level! The level will be reflected on your badge, that will be upgraded to a Circularity Label.
6. HOOP social: feel free to use the social media cards attached on your channels with the following hashtag and messaging on Twitter for example:

We are proud to be vitalising Europe's #urbanbioeconomy with other #cities and #regions. Join HOOP and stay in the loop! <https://hoopproject.eu/network/> #biowaste #wastewater #circulareconomy #GreenDeal #ClimatePact

7. HOOP print: You can also request the label in higher resolution for a print publication such as a report or a flyer. Please contact media@hoopproject.eu or your HOOP communication contact point for the higher resolution .jpg or .eps file.
8. HOOP assets: we will make available different HOOP communication materials that you can request to be delivered as well, such as stickers, magnet lapel pins, and drink coasters. These branding materials add to the indirect outreach of the HOOP Network and may prompt replicability.
9. HOOP campaign: we may ask you to participate in the HOOP Circularity Label campaign to announce your participation/achievement levels at a given time together with the other members of the HOOP Network in order to create a cluster-and-ripple effect to attract more cities and regions to join.
10. HOOP media: if you are interested you can also prepare a special media alert or press release that you can adapt to your language and local environment and city/region efforts at a given date as well so we our outreach multiplies with your networks as well.

Stay tuned for more and thank you again for joining the HOOP Network!

These 10 main points of the 2-page HOOP Membership Label Comms Guidelines will be complemented with a .zip file or Trello link including the different online shareables, and materials/assets in different formats for new and existing members to refer to when communicating about HOOP. This will be provided in an easily accessible manner.

5. Conclusions and next steps

Already around 30 Cities and Regions have joined the HOOP Network. Each of them have received some simple materials (project logo, social media visuals) and advice to help advertise their involvement in the network and their association with the project.

In the coming weeks and months further development of the Membership and Circularity Label will continue in close cooperation with Task 7.1.

Within Task 7.1 the set of indicators to evaluate the circularity level is under construction, and will be validated with the HOOP Lighthouses. After the validation process is complete a final set will be chosen to create the evaluation tool. At the moment, it seems that two sets of indicators will be offered: one to evaluate the circularity of Organic Fraction of Municipal Solid Waste (OFMSW) management and one for the circularity of wastewater management. Therefore two Circularity Labels are finally expected.

The definitive designs for the Label will be made available to Cities and Regions when Task 7.1 will be finalised, at which point an updated version of this document will be prepared.